

Polymer Association in Dilute Solution Through Polar End Groups*

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The problem of molecular weight determination of polymers containing ammonium salt groups at the ends of the molecules has been investigated. Tetrahydrofuran is regarded as the suitable solvent for the determination of \bar{M}_n of such polymers. Polymers with isothiuronium salt as end group were found to be significantly associated in toluene, while little or no association in toluene was observed with polymers bearing tertiary ammonium salt as end group. Association in dilute solutions of carboxyl ended polystyrene was noted only for lower molecular weight (around 30,000) polymers.

Reactions analogous to those occurring in small molecular systems are quite common in the field of macromolecules. This is also true for molecular association reactions which frequently involve forces physical in character. A few examples are cited. Hydroxyl ended polystyrene forms H-bonded molecular associates just like alcohols in nonpolar solvents^{1,2}. Similarly, copolymers of styrene or methylmethacrylate and methacrylic acid undergo intra- as well as inter-molecular H-bonding association in hydrocarbon solvents^{3,4}. Association other than via H-bond as observed in the solution of alkylammonium salts^{5,6} and also soaps⁷ in nonpolar solvents involves dipole dipole attraction forces. While polymer association through carboxylate groups has been studied by some workers^{8,9} we are not aware of any such work on polymers carrying a few ammonium salt groups. We became interested in this problem in connection with our work on the estimation of amine groups in polymers.

Furthermore, polymer association presents problems for the determination of molecular weight of polymers. While it is certain that the extent and size of molecular associates in solution depend on the solute concentration, it is frequently reported that association persists even at the lowest concentration levels of polymers (ca. below 10^{-4} mole/l) usually employed in osmometric work. The result is that the reduced pressure extrapolated to infinite dilution does not eliminate the effect of intermolecular association^{1,3,5}. Proper selection of solvent can only lead to correct estimation of molecular weights. In this work we have examined the problem of molecular weight determination vis-a-vis association of polymers containing a few types of ammonium salts as end groups. A few molecular weight data for polymers bearing carboxyl end groups have also been included.

* Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth anniversary.

EXPERIMENTAL

Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) with $\overset{+}{N}H(C_2H_5)_2Cl^-$ end group: Samples 1 and 2 were prepared by polymerizing MMA in aqueous medium (pH 3.5) at room temperature using the initiator system, N-chlorodiethylamine (prepared *in situ*) and Mohr's salt. Samples 3, 4 and 5 were prepared using the initiator system, triethylamine+chlorine+Mohr's salt. These latter samples contained quaternary ammonium as well as tertiary ammonium end groups in about equal proportions¹⁰.

Polymers with $SC(= \overset{+}{N}H_2)NH_2Cl^-$ end group: These were prepared using the redox initiator system Fe(III) and thiourea^{11,12}. Polymerization of styrene was carried out in the mixed solvent, *t*-butyl alcohol+water, while MMA was polymerized homogeneously in *t*-butyl alcohol medium.

All the above polymers were purified by precipitation from benzene solutions into acidified (HCl) methanol. Acid is omitted in the final precipitation step. It is believed that this treatment converts all basic groups in polymers into corresponding hydrochlorides. The polymers were dried in a vacuum oven at 40°.

Polymers with COOH end group: These were prepared by polymerizing MMA and styrene at 60° in dimethylformamide using 4,4'-azo-bis-4-cyanovaleric acid as initiator. Samples 12 and 13 were obtained by polymerizing styrene thermally at 60° in the presence of thioglycolic acid. It is expected that this latter process introduces one carboxyl group per polystyrene molecule.

Fig. 1. Plot of $(\pi/c)^{1/2}$ vs. c , π in cm of solvent, c in g/l.

○ THF ● TOLUENE

Osmometric measurements were carried out at 30° in a hp 501 high speed membrane osmometer using 08 membrane. Solvents used were toluene and tetrahydrofuran (THF). Analytical reagent grade toluene was used straight. THF was dried over KOH, treated with hydroquinone and then distilled. π/c vs c plots are not linear in every case; for such samples $(\pi/c)^{\dagger}$ vs. c plots, however gave linear plots. The slopes are positive in every case. Some representative plots are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 2. Plot of π/c vs. c , π in cm of solvent, c in g/l.
 ● TOLUENE ○ THF

Viscosity measurements were carried out in benzene at 30° using a Ubbelohde viscometer. \bar{M}_v was calculated from the equations

$$\bar{M}_n = 1.78 \times 10^5 (\eta)^{1.37} \text{ for unfractionated polystyrene}^{13}$$

and

$$[\eta] = 8.69 \times 10^{-5} (\bar{M}_n)^{0.76} \text{ for unfractionated PMMA}^{14}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PMMA with $\overset{+}{N}H(C_2H_5)_2Cl^-$ end group: Number average molecular weights of these polymers as determined in toluene and tetrahydrofuran are recorded in Table I. The values in toluene are higher than those obtained in THF to the extent of 5–20%. Part of this difference might be accounted for due to some possible systematic experimental error. However, the result indicates that association of such polymers, if any, in toluene is not significant. In toluene the simplest entity for the salt group is the ion pair between the ammonium ion and the halide ion. Dissociation of the ion pairs to free ions is unlikely in this solvent characterized by low dielectric constant and absence of any significant specific chemical interaction with ions. For long chain tertiaryammonium chlorides such as tributylammonium chloride and triethylammonium chloride it has been shown⁶ that the respective ion pairs have considerable dipole moments (about 7–8 D) and these are in need of

TABLE 1

Molecular weight data of PMMA with $\overset{+}{N}H(C_2H_5)_2Cl^-$ end group

Sample No.	Polymer	$\bar{M}_n \times 10^{-4}$		$\bar{M}_v \times 10^{-4}$	
		THF	Toluene		
1	PMMA	3.05	3.19	1.05	3.75
2	„	5.00	5.80	1.16	7.36
3	„	58.60	61.80	1.05	—
4	„	15.40	18.50	1.20	20.32
5	„	13.40	15.60	1.16	14.56

further solvation in zero dipole moment solvents such as benzene. Because of the failure on the part of the solvent to provide the necessary solvation, the ion pairs tend to solvate themselves mutually through dipole dipole association¹⁵⁻¹⁸. A series of multimers may be formed depending on concentration⁶. The same explanation applies for the association of the polymers in toluene. On the other hand, the ion pairs are expected to be efficiently solvated in THF ($\epsilon = 7.58^{19}$, $\mu = 1.71^{20}$ at 25°). Moreover, the ether oxygen in THF is a center of specific interaction with the ammonium proton. Such specific interaction between the ether oxygen in anisole and the ammonium proton in trilaurylammonium salts has been envisaged by Bucher and Diamond¹⁷. All these support the view that the ion pairs and hence the polymers are not aggregated in THF. We presume also that neither do the ion pairs dissociate in THF. This contention found support in the observation¹⁷ that certain tertiary-ammonium salts do not dissociate in the concentration range of interest here in solvents like *o*-dichlorobenzene ($\epsilon = 9.93^{17}$; $\mu = 2.25^{20}$) and in anisole ($\epsilon = 4.33^{17}$; $\mu = 1.23^{20}$). THF is expected to behave like these solvents.

Thus, we held that molecular weights determined in THF are the true values. The ratio of the molecular weights obtained in toluene to that in THF gives the average aggregation number (\bar{n}) of the polymeric ammonium salts. These are included in Table 1. The average degree of association for these salts is not significantly large. This is not unexpected because considerable H-bonding interaction between the ammonium proton and the halide ion^{17,18,21} exists. This sort of interaction reduces considerably the need for solvation of the ion pairs through mutual aggregation^{17,18}. It may be of some interest to compare the degree of aggregation with that observed for ammonium salts of much shorter chain length. Thus, dimer association constant for trilaurylammonium chloride is of the order¹⁵ of 20 M^{-1} at 25°. This means that at 10^{-4} molar concentration of the salt the dimer accounts for only about 0.02%. In this perspective absence of any significant association of the polymeric tertiary ammonium salt in toluene is not unlikely.

Polymers with SC ($= \overset{+}{N}H_2NH_2Cl^-$ end group: As the data in Table 2 shows, these polymers exhibit considerable aggregation in toluene. The molecular weights of these polymers determined in toluene are about 2-3 times as high as those determined in THF. To our knowledge, studies on the aggregation of isothiuronium or amidinium salts in nonpolar

solvents do not exist in literature. Neither are the aggregation data for primary or secondary ammonium salts in nonpolar solvents available. Presumably, the low solubility of

TABLE 2

Molecular weight data for polymers with $SC(=NH_2)NH_2Cl^-$ end group

Sample No.	Polymer	$\bar{M}_n \times 10^{-5}$		\bar{n}	$\bar{M}_v \times 10^{-5}$
		THF	Toluene		
6	Polystyrene	4.10	10.30	2.5	9.28
7	„	2.46	5.41	2.2	4.20
8	„	1.36	2.77	2.0	3.05
9	„	1.50	4.20	2.7	—
10	PMMA	1.83	3.12	1.7	1.67
11	„	1.32	3.48	2.6	2.10

such compounds in nonpolar solvents presents experimental difficulty. No comparison of the present data with low molecular weight compounds is therefore possible. However, Diamond²² predicted that aggregation of primary and secondary salts should be greater than that of tertiary because the greater number of hydrogen in the former salts “might allow for a more extensive hydrogen bonded network and so greater aggregation”. The greater aggregation observed for the isothiuronium salts here seems to support this contention.

We have further support for the aggregation of these polymers in toluene from the estimation of end groups of these polymers²³. Use of the molecular weight data obtained in toluene leads to unreasonably higher values of the number of end groups per polymer molecule. However, if the molecular weight data in THF are used, the results become reasonable.

Polymers with Carboxyl end group: Out of the five polystyrene samples reported in Table 3, two are unfractionated and the rest fractionated. Examination of the results for

TABLE 3

Molecular weight data for polymers with COOH end group

Sample No.	Polymer	$\bar{M}_n \times 10^{-4}$		\bar{n}
		THF	Toluene	
12 ^u	Polystyrene	6.20	8.09	1.30
13 ^u	„	7.00	9.06	1.30
14 ^f	„	3.30	4.92	1.50
15 ^f	„	9.80	10.80	1.10
16 ^f	„	6.44	6.86	1.06
17 ^u	PMMA	18.80	21.60	1.15

u—unfractionated; *f*—fractionated.

the fractionated samples shows that aggregation, if any, is significant only in the low molecular weight range (around 30,000). Melville *et al.*²⁴ found that association of carboxyl ended poly(vinyl acetate) is noteworthy only when the molecular weight of the polymer is low (< 10,000). Data in Table 3 also shows that aggregation in an unfractionated polymer is greater than in a fractionated sample of similar molecular weight. This is perhaps due to the fact that the unfractionated samples contain some amount of polymers of lower molecular weights.

Viscosity average molecular weights: These are included in the tables 1-2 to give an idea how these data compare with the value of \bar{M}_n obtained in THF. Constants of the Mark-Houwink equation are chosen so that \bar{M}_v is more representative of \bar{M}_n than of \bar{M}_w . It appears that agreement between \bar{M}_v and \bar{M}_n is reasonable in those cases where aggregation was found to be little or absent. Polymers with isothiuronium salt as end group show maximum discrepancy between M_n and M_v values.

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